

PEDAGOGICAL MODEL OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL AND GENERAL CULTURAL COMPETENCIES IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, Pedagogical model of preparation of future teachers for the development of national and general cultural competences in students are studied, its necessity and pedagogical foundations are detailed.

Key words: pedagogue, professional competence, classification, improvement, competence, competent approach, national and general cultural competences, model.

INTRODUCTION. The process of a growing person's consistent rise to humanistic spiritual and moral values and ideals requires certain intellectual and emotional-volitional actions from him. At the same time, the student's conscious internal behavior should become a habit for his social and spiritual existence and behavior. Only then it will be possible to emphasize the formation of the foundations of the national and general cultural competence of this person and the national values that are its component. Therefore, the pedagogical management of the process of developing general cultural competence of future teachers should be based on the circumstances that encourage them to perform actions that correspond to the content of the national culture.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Issues of development of socio-cultural activity among future teachers in Uzbekistan M. Rakhmanova, M. Kuronov, H. Tojiboyeva, G.J. Tulenova, Q. Quranboyev; N. Abdumuratova, D. Nafasov regarding the development of socio-cultural competence; historical-philosophical, ethical-aesthetic content of spiritual and artistic values, O. Abdurakhmonov, D. Yakibova, R. Mavlonova, N. Rakhmonkulova have conducted studies on the development of thinking capabilities of learners based on the person-oriented approach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In the process of modeling, the identification of organizational tasks (approximate forms and methods of organizing the activities of learners) is built on the basis of creating good pedagogical conditions and requires the continuous assimilation of historical, socio-cultural ideals of the individual and the formation of a modern professional and national and universal model of competence. .

In our opinion, within the framework of our research, future teachers will learn methods and technologies that require national and cross-cultural activities, as well as comparison, analogy, classification, application of a model, finding contradictions and overcoming them, induction. and should be taught to use scientific methods such as deduction.

In the pedagogical system of preparing future teachers for the process of developing national and general cultural competence, technologies that help increase student activity can be divided into three blocks:

1. Motivational appeal - taking into account the personal characteristics and interests of students, interest, desire to engage in independent activities, creativity, a combination of innovative active and interactive methods - problem, project, pedagogical and business situations and games, biographical method (of famous people personal insights about their biographies and destinies) etc.

2. Complex psychological - exposure to all analyzers, use of various verbal, visual, auditory tools, modern lesson forms - video lesson, video conference, quest, excursion, etc.; involving students in socio-cultural practices, individual, group and public forms of social and cultural activity.

3. Historical-cultural - enriching the "cultural space" of students with the news of society, country, world culture - the level of knowledge and understanding of the nature and meaning of knowledge, historical events, social changes, cultural events of Uzbekistan - practical with museum culture introduction, experiences of participation in holidays, customs, traditions, attitude to cultural achievements, national manners, mentality, way of life, revealing universal values in national forms.

Preparation of future teachers for the process of national and general cultural competence development requires constant control (monitoring) and thus becomes complex. Monitoring indicators are as follows:

- a) development of the level of national and general cultural knowledge and skills of future teachers;
- b) success or ineffectiveness of used methods and technologies;
- c) corrective works.

These indicators should be determined by evaluating the educational and creative tasks performed in the classroom, in the independent work process, conducting tests, questionnaires, and questioning students to determine the level and content of motivation in the process of mastering socio-cultural competence.

Observations of the student in this way show gradual changes in his outlook, motivation, purposefulness, intellectual and spiritual-moral development, awareness of national and universal cultural values and their development, growth of professional skills. allows to reach. Creation of a model of formation of professional and socio-cultural competence oriented to modern practice is built on the basis of creating favorable pedagogical conditions for directing the individual to the continuous development of the historical, cultural, spiritual and moral ideals of his people.

One of the ways of improving the system of preparing future teachers for the process of developing national and general cultural competence is the use of "Alternative environment" in the course of the lesson. The word "alternative" means the choice of one or more options by the author. In our work, we have two directions in the course of the lesson: the first is to reveal an alternative situation in which national and intercultural relations have arisen in the process; the second is to analyze the different evaluations of past events, national relations, and general cultural relations in different literatures.

Within the framework of the model, the work of learning and systematizing the material in the educational and research activity of learners is of great importance. In the analysis of the "alternative environment" the support of the professor is needed, because students are not always ready for the analysis of general cultural and historical-artistic publications, in most cases they evaluate and think at the level of daily, ordinary life.

Thinking about "alternative environments" is a type of problem-based learning. Its use in the course of the lesson requires the fulfillment of a number of methodological conditions: "alternative environment" should provide a solution to the leading educational issues, the scientific orientation of students:

- the first type of environment includes alternatives that can really exist in the process of national and universal relations;
- influencing the formation of the national-historical and universal consciousness of learners by emphasizing the past assessment in the second type of environment;
- proposed alternatives should be understandable for students to understand and analyze;
- teaching in the analysis of "alternative environment" should be carried out step by step, that is, after acquiring theoretical knowledge, criteria for analyzing the process of national and intercultural relations will be developed, students' thinking activity will become more complex.

The following technology of working with "alternative environment" was used by searching and choosing good methods of education according to the specified characteristics:

- creation of selection environment;
- understanding of educational tasks by students;
- determination of the criteria for consideration of the proposed alternatives;
- analysis and evaluation according to the selected criteria;
- based proposals of future teachers regarding the studied problem;
- analysis of the results of student work by the teacher.

In applying the model of cognitive processes of students' scientific research, the teacher helps the student to choose his future creative work, taking into account not only his personal interests, but also his level of training and real possibilities.

Today, pedagogues are moving away from traditional education to work on the problems of analyzing interrelated academic subjects, such as history and literature, history and philosophy, history and world art culture. is barking. The model of dialogue activities requires conducting lessons in a dialogue form. For this purpose, situational issues (assignments) are designed: choosing conflicting issues, solving situational problems, looking for the reasoning of certain facts and events, solving problems with different answers, putting forward hypotheses.

The mentioned methodological methods allow dialogic relations between teachers and students, their main features are reflected in the following:

- participants of the educational process are considered subjects of mutual relations;
- there is a clash of opinions of the participants of the educational activity;
- incompleteness of the dialogue, differences of opinion during the discussion of the problem.

It allows to solve the problem of synthesizing the didactic and personal aspects of the preparation of future teachers for the process of developing national and general cultural competence.

The model of educational creative activity covers the following parts:

- allows future teachers to determine the main and private issues themselves;
- choosing and applying appropriate methods of solving problems (the ability to choose solutions and tools);

- implementation of independent control of the choice of effective methods of solving the problem.

In our research work, we used several options for creative study of problematic situations related to national and cross-cultural relations:

- organization of problem education;
- organizing work with complex methodical documents;
- teaching to solve creative problems;
- organization of game education (teaching);
- organization of dialogic education.

By "creative task" we understand such a task (problem) in which the problem solving algorithm is unknown to students. In this case, the teacher offers students to solve unknown problems.

Future teachers are not required to memorize a certain amount of information, but independently research, search, find and explain ways to solve problems. So, in this case, students do not remember ready-made constructions, but invent it themselves based on their existing knowledge. Also, students' completion of problems of different levels of difficulty allows the teacher to assess the level of development of the student.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it can be concluded that the preparation of future teachers for the process of developing students' national and general cultural competence can be carried out based on the effective use of effective educational approaches and modeling opportunities that show concrete results, effective application of innovative methods and educational technologies.

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